

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' NATURAL SCIENCE LITERACY BASED ON THE INTEGRATION OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL LEARNING IN THE COURSE “FUNDAMENTALS OF ECOLOGY”

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ABSTRACT

The article examines issues related to the development of students' natural science literacy in the process of teaching the course “Fundamentals of Ecology” in higher education institutions through the integration of theoretical knowledge and practical activities. The content, structure, and effectiveness of a methodological system developed on the basis of competency-based and activity-oriented approaches are described. The results of the experimental study demonstrated positive changes in the formation of students' ecological thinking, their ability to apply scientific concepts, analyze problem situations, and make well-founded decisions.

Introduction

In the global educational context, improving environmental education, fostering students' conscious attitudes toward nature, and developing their natural science literacy are among the priority tasks. In modern education, it is not sufficient for students to possess only theoretical knowledge; their ability to apply this knowledge in practical situations is of great importance. In this regard, the development of natural science literacy through ensuring the integration of theoretical and practical learning in teaching the course “Fundamentals of Ecology” emerges as an актуал scientific and pedagogical problem.

Research methodology

The following methods were used in the course of the study:

analysis of pedagogical literature;
observation of the educational process;
questionnaires and testing;
experimental research;
statistical analysis.

The methodology developed in the study was based on integrating theoretical knowledge with practical classes, laboratory work, case analysis, and tasks oriented toward solving environmental problems. The main components of the methodological system included:

the content of theoretical knowledge;
practice-oriented tasks;

assessment and diagnostic criteria.

At the same time, the research methodology was aimed at scientifically substantiating a methodological system that ensures the integration of theoretical and practical activities in the educational process and the development of students' natural science literacy. The methodology relies on modern pedagogical theories, the competency-based approach, and the principles of activity-oriented learning.

1. Methodological approaches

The study was conducted based on the following main methodological approaches:

1. Competency-based approach

The competency-based approach implies the formation of not only knowledge in students but also their ability to apply it in practical activities.

Example: Within the course "Fundamentals of Ecology," on the topic "Pollution of Water Resources," students were given the following tasks:

- to identify sources of pollution of a local river or canal;
- to analyze the consequences of pollution from ecological and social perspectives;
- to develop practical proposals for solving the problem.

These tasks contributed to the development of students' competencies in scientific analysis, ecological thinking, and decision-making.

2. Activity-oriented approach

This approach ensures students' participation in the educational process not as passive listeners but as active researchers.

Example: On the topic "Ecosystems and Their Stability," a laboratory session was organized during which students:

- created a model of an artificial ecosystem;
- observed the impact of external factors;
- analyzed the obtained results using tables and diagrams.

3. Integrative approach

The integration of ecology with biology, chemistry, geography, and economics ensures a holistic perception of knowledge.

Example: Within the topic "Atmospheric Pollution," the following aspects were studied in an integrated manner:

- the composition of chemical pollutants (chemistry);
- atmospheric circulation (geography);
- impacts on human health (biology).

2. Research methods

The following scientific and pedagogical methods were applied in the study:

1. Theoretical analysis method

National and international sources related to environmental education, natural science literacy, and competency-based education were analyzed.

Example: The model of natural science literacy used in PISA studies was analyzed and adapted to the content of the discipline "Ecology."

2. Observation Method

During the educational process, the following were systematically observed:

students' activity levels;
independence in performing practical tasks;
the level of ecological thinking.

3. Questionnaire and Testing Methods

Diagnostic tools were developed to determine students' levels of knowledge and skills.

Sample questions:

"Can you use scientific knowledge when solving environmental problems?"

"Do you experience difficulties in applying theoretical knowledge in practical situations?"

4. Pedagogical Experiment Method

The experimental research was conducted in diagnostic, formative, and final stages:

at the diagnostic stage, the initial level of students' literacy was determined;

at the formative stage, the developed methodology was implemented;

at the final stage, the obtained results were analyzed.

5. Statistical Analysis Method

The obtained results were processed using mathematical and statistical methods.

Example: The results of the experimental and control groups were compared using average indicators, and growth dynamics were determined.

3. Organization of the methodological system

The developed methodology included the following components:

theoretical knowledge (lectures, electronic resources);

practical activities (laboratory work, case analysis, project-based learning);

assessment and diagnostics (rubrics, tests, portfolios).

Example: On the topic "Solid Household Waste," students:

studied theoretical material;

analyzed a local waste management problem;

developed a waste recycling project.

Research results. The experimental research was conducted with the participation of students from higher education institutions. During the learning process, theoretical classes were combined with practical research, analysis of environmental situations, and problem-solving tasks. As a result, a significant increase was observed in the following indicators:

systematic formation of ecological knowledge;

development of skills for the practical application of natural science concepts;

increased ability to analyze environmental problems and make scientifically grounded decisions.

The results of the statistical analysis confirmed that the level of natural science literacy in the experimental group was higher compared to that of the control group.

Discussion. The obtained results indicate that the methodology based on the integration of theoretical and practical learning ensures active student participation in the learning process, contributes to the formation of ecological thinking, and enhances the sustainability of educational outcomes. This fully corresponds to the requirements of the competency-based approach and contributes to improving the effectiveness of environmental education.

Conclusion. Thus, the implementation of a methodology based on the integration of theoretical and practical learning in teaching the course “Fundamentals of Ecology” ensures high effectiveness in developing students’ natural science literacy. The research results confirm the scientific and practical significance of this methodology and its applicability in the practice of higher education institutions.

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